

Preservation and Conservation of Library Material

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Abstract:

In third world countries, Libraries despite the restrictions of finance confronting them still make huge investment on acquisition of library resources. One of the greatest challenges are deterioration of library resources which plaguing the libraries. From a massive loss of her heritage, it should be savage these library resources and libraries and these study examines preservation and conservation of library material. The library security is most used measure of preservation and conservation practices that is reveal by finding. The deterioration of library material has greatest causes which is dust and particular matter. The finding further revealed that dusting, cleaning and proper shelving are major techniques which is adopted by libraries. In this study, has examined the causes of deterioration patterns of library and evaluates its preservation.

Keywords: Preservation, Conservation, Libraries, Shelving

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Introduction

Library is an ocean of knowledge, in which different books lingers the essence of knowledge and information. A well-equipped library provides education and general information that is needed by teachers, students etc.

Preservation of library is very important in order to maintain and store the information which is written in even in very old books. Library and information management contain important aspect that is preservation and conservation practices and techniques of library. Any loss of such material is simply irreplaceable; therefore, preservation and conservation of library and books is really important. Book repairs, bookbinding, conservation treatment and emergency preparedness and response are included in conservation. In conservation department, deterioration materials are needed to repair by binding or protective enclosures.

Library material facing basic challenges that is deterioration of information materials which are prone to wear and tear, cracks, wrapping, shrinkage, brittleness, discoloration, hole, dust, bio-infestation, abrasion and dirt accumulation. Poor handling of library material is the root cause.

External Factors causes Deterioration

This type of deterioration contain main elements which are the result of moisture, light, heat, pollution, temperature, poor handling of information resources, insects etc.

Moisture

Moisture really effects the quality of books and other articles as it proves to be a kind of necessary evil because some amount of moisture is required for the maintenance of the flexibility of the paper, however moisture favours the growth of microorganisms which is responsible for the deterioration of library stock

Heat/Temperature

Low temperature helps in maintaining the quality of articles and books. Thus helps in the preservation of library. As high temperature high humidity favours the growth of microorganisms, low temperature is required to prevent deterioration.

Light

According to this paper, ultraviolet radiation and visible light causing dislocation, fading and embrittlement to library information resources. Low intensity lights cause least destruction of library articulates. The quality of light transmitted by windows is controllable with curtains, tinted glass, shades and louvers.

Pollutions

Dust and other pollutants usually encourage the growth of micro-organisms and also deteriorate the quality and physical appearance of the book. Hence proper dusting and cleaning of library premises as well books should be done on a regular basis

Human Factor

In libraries, human factors are most important factor because improper handling and storage practices created the deterioration of library. Therefore one should know how to handle library materials which is the basic rule for preservation.

Insufficient Space

Insufficient space cause books to be kept in a suffocating manner which results in piling of books and articles. This henceforth results in loss of ventilation and books tend to stick to each other and this causes the deterioration of pages and written part of the articles.

Biological agents/Factors

Complete destruction occurs in few holes that may have common types of insects which attack on paper, these insects are: Termites, Cockroaches, Silverfish, Booklice, Bookbeetles and Booklice. They feed on cellulose which is the main component of paper thereby making them rot and turns the pages pale.

Disasters

Due to disasters, damage or destroy a few items or entire collections that can result from fire, earthquakes, storms, flooding and broken steam pipes. Disasters are generally unpredictable but one should build such a library where provision are present in order to minimize the loss caused by disasters.

Techniques of Preservation and Conservation of Library

To preserving of information resources in library that are usable which is as follows:

- Repairs
- Air Conditioning
- Fumigation
- Firefighting equipment
- Reformatting
- Binding
- Proper storage
- Use of insecticides
- Digitization
- Photocopying/duplication
- Storage of books away from light
- Application of fungicides
- Encapsulation
- Deacidification
- Microfilming
- Digitization
- Insurance
- Lamination

Preservation policies at Library

According to International Organization for Standardization (ISO), "All the organizations need to identify the regulatory environment that affects their activities and requirements to document their activities".

Paper based Documents are preserved

Preservation of paper-based collection of library such as books, journals, maps etc. that is meaning of preservation of paper based documents. Preservation of paper-based documents have two basic principal methods, first one is preservation of original format by number of techniques such as good handling that is combined with sound protective storage; cold storage for selected materials conservation and restoration treatment and mass Deacidification.

Second one is reformatting, in which complete conversion of material into other format is done to preserve the library's collections. It also include digitization and microfilming.

Digital-based Documents are preserved

Written materials are converted into digital formats and then preserved as a record or e-book. This increase the durability of books and other library materials. Digital resources are preserved by using four approaches or strategies which are: refreshing (periodic copying from one physical medium to another), technology preservation (replicating any old configuration of hardware and software), migration and encapsulation.

Preservation of Information Resources

In the process of managing information resources, preservation is a crucial element in the library. The main of preservation is to extend the life span of information resources. For deterioration and decay of information resources, several factors are responsible in libraries. To preserve libraries, its responsibilities given to the maximal use of teachers, students and its communities. Some factors are responsible for loss of information resources from libraries include high temperature, biological agents, environmental condition, human agents and both natural and artificial disaster. Preservation of information resources divided into two aspects:

Review of Literature

Olatokun 2008, stated that institutional libraries use the digital method to preserve the library materials to stay for a long time in meeting information needs of users. In libraries and archives, digitization method is widely used to find the solution of problem of information preservation. This method is quite expensive. Such polices of preservation and conservation of library resources need to be implemented and reviewed from time to time to cater for new challenges and emerging technologies.

OGUNSOLA 2016, stated that printed material are preserved through humidity control and temperature regulation but non-print materials are preserved under more rigorous preservation and storage condition, proper handling and disaster management controls. The preserving the libraries by using methods in non-book materials are; cleaning, installing air conditioner, shelving and adequate security.

Ambika and Begum 2017, dictated that most of the colleges and universities library are suffering from lack of funding, improper infrastructure facilities, lack of knowledge about of preservation and conservation, techniques, practices, untrained manpower skills how to handle the preservation and conservation techniques, no written policy, outward hardware and software, administrative problem etc.

Osunride and Adetunla 2017, stated that this study has concluded that due to the lack of proper preservation and conservation practices in Universities and colleges, causes of resource loss and deterioration. Greatest cause of information resources deterioration, dust and particulate matter was found. Greater relative humidity, high acidity level, wear and tear mark and high temperature level have significant effect on library material.

Conclusion

Libraries have done own very best to overcome the main challenges of preservation and conservation of information resources. Libraries are deteriorate by some external factors like light, pollution, pest, human factor etc. for which apply the technique due to which some deterioration are removed. In some universities and colleges, library staff were not have opportunity for inter-state training or international training on preservation of information resources. Library can be utilized in their best way to keep the library in a good way by giving orientation to them frequently about everyday care and handling with preservation and conservation.

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